

Streaming and Stratification in the Berlin System of Education and Their Conclusion for Teachers and Teaching

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For the last three years, before I arrived in Canada, I have worked for a private tuition company. It was less about the money, as I was just starting at Potsdam University. Instead it was more about the company participating in a governmental program I was interested in. The program is called “Bildung und Teilhabe” and would directly translate to “Education and Participation”, while a better translation would rather be “Participation in Education”. In Berlin, every family that receives social security benefits or can prove a low socio-economic status can apply for the “Berlin-Pass” for all of their family members. All school children with a “Berlin-Pass” get their private tuition expenses covered by the government, if they take their private tuition lessons at participating companies like the one I worked for. In short, I could teach pupils that otherwise could not pay for private tuition. In my mind I helped to slowly balance equality in opportunity.

At a similar time I started to get more active at my faculty. I became a voted member of a committee with the goal to design a new study program for science teachers. After one of the first sessions, when everybody was still getting to know each other, I stayed after a committee meeting to talk to one of my professors about equality in opportunity in education. Eventually, we stumbled across my job and I told him what I was doing and that I thought it was an important work. But the professor somewhat stole my thunder. In his opinion, the existence of such a program like “Bildung und Teilhabe” is barely more than the proof of all the shortcomings and failure in the Berlin education system. He convinced me to some extent and I saw approached the problem from a new angle. What I did, might help to reduce the problem temporarily, but it will never solve it. I started to dig deeper into the topic of the relation between a low SES¹ of pupils and their obstacles to find success in education. As long as the Berlin education systems does not overcome its weaknesses regarding low SES pupils, local teachers have to be aware of the streaming and stratification in it to

1 SES – socio-economic status

counteract the obstruction it provides to low SES pupils, as equality in opportunity in education is their right.

The Current Political Situation

In early July of 2019 the German Federal Ministry for Education and Research published their official result of the G7 meeting in Paris. They want to stand up for “[equal educational opportunities for all children]”, no matter if poor or rich. The current situation is very different. According to report of the Federal Centre for Political Education Germany in 2018, educational opportunities vary between different social-economic status groups. Significantly more than one out of two children with two academic parents finish school with the highest possible degree. For children of working class parents on the other hand, it is most likely that they will work in a field similar to their parents. Assuming that having academic parents doesn't make a child smarter by default, this seems to be off. While the problem is growing in popularity, the report states that conservative politicians perceive true equality in opportunity in education as unachievable.

A major measuring tool for equality in educational opportunity are the OECD reports about recent PISA studies, especially when it comes to the influence of the SES of pupils. According to the OECD report about PISA in 2009, Germany scored a variance score of 18 that can be traced back on SES influence. In the following 2013 PISA study the variance score decreased to 15.6 and in the most recent 2015 PISA study the variance score slightly increased to 16. For comparison, Canada achieved a variance score of 9 in 2015. While the German score is over all decreasing since 2009, it is still struggling to change significantly. Therefore, equality in educational opportunities still requires major work to significantly improve in Germany.

The Current System of Education in Berlin

Education in Berlin is partitioned into three major sections. It starts with Primary education followed by Secondary *I* education and voluntary Secondary *II* education. The regular school-leaving qualification is the MSA after grade 10. Depending on your marks, it enables you to work in

the majority of jobs, to apply for an apprenticeship or to continue school a Secondary *II* school. Finishing Secondary *II* school awards you with the *Abitur*, the general university entrance qualification, or the *Fachabitur*, the restricted university entrance qualification.

According to the official website of the Berlin senate on the Berlin education system, the usual school career looks as follows. On average, children start school at age five to six. After two flexible introductory school years, grade 3 is the first year for most Primary school pupils to receive marks. Secondary *I* school starts at grade 7 and there is the choice between the advanced high school and the ISS (Integrated Secondary School), the basic high school. The major difference between the advanced and the basic high school is, that every pupil on the advanced high school is expected to continue school into Secondary *II* school to receive the general university entrance qualification. Pupils attending the basic high school can continue school to earn the general university entrance qualification, but it will take them one additional year and they are required to have a certain mark average only 1 in 5 pupils of the basic high school obtains.

Pupils may leave the Primary school early and start attending the advanced high school at grade 5, if their marks are exceptional. In general, the step from Primary school to Secondary *I* school might be the most significant. The Berlin senate specifically released an official guideline on which type of school to attend after Primary school. The mark average of a pupil at the end of grade 5 as well as the mark average after the first term of grade 6 is most decisive for this process. While pupils with a mark average of 2.1 or better are recommended to attend the advanced high school, pupils with a mark average of 2.8 or worse are recommended to attend the basic high school. Only for pupils in between, additional factors are taken into consideration. However, advanced high schools have the option to send pupils to a basic high school if they can not keep their mark average on what is expected of them.

Streaming and Stratification in Education

On page 276 of their book *The Schooled Society* (2018), Scott Davies and Neil Guppy define streaming as “[a] highly structured form of ability grouping that directs students into distinct paths”. The two key terms of that definition are “ability” and “distinct”. While ability is a neutral term on its own, ability in education is not. Especially the measuring of ability is strongly connected to the equality in educational opportunity. Do all pupils have equal conditions to grow and show their ability? It behaves similar for the term distinct. Distinction on its own, does not refer to one being better or worse than the other, just different. Distinction in education connected with ability in education does refer to a difference in performance and accomplishment. Therefore, the term streaming in education refers to distinction based on pupils performance regarding their ability as it is measured by the education system. Here the term stratification comes into play. On the same page as streaming, Davies and Guppy define stratification as “[a] concept of inequality as a hierarchical ladder with finely gradated degrees”. The term ladder portrays the issue exceptionally good. As soon as the a distinction is based on measuring, a ranking of performance, accomplishments and ability is created. The term inequality just adds to the picture. How can the ladder and its degrees be fair, if the distinction is based on the measuring of ability in education? All of this still does not even bring up the question what kind of knowledge and ability is considered valuable and worth to be measured.

Implications for Teachers and Teaching

So what is the conclusion in the large picture of the three previous chapters? On page 103 and 104 of *The Schooled Society* Davies and Guppy emphasize the influence of the SES of pupils on their performance, accomplishments and success in Primary school. “[Children] from wealthier families are better prepared for school from the very first day of class” (Davies and Guppy, 2018). Children from low income families experience delays literacy and vocabulary. Similar trends continue for teenagers. To reduce the negative influence of the SES of pupils in education when it comes to

performance and accomplishments is something the politic is still struggling with. While the variance score in the PISA studies is slowly changing for the better and Germany wants to step up for equality in educational opportunity, the SES influence is still significant. Now combined with the Berlin education system that starts streaming into basic and advanced high schools as early as age 10, low SES pupils have a considerably harder time to have equal educational opportunities. They start with a disadvantage in abilities considered worth measuring, have very little time to catch up in an education system struggling to provide equality in opportunity. How likely are they to achieve a placement at an advanced high school. Their disadvantage in abilities like literacy and vocabulary are likely to continue when they are teenagers. How likely are they to stay at an advanced high school?

As stated above, significantly more than one out of two children with two academic parents finish school with the highest possible degree. For children of working class parents on the other hand, it is most likely that they will work in a field similar to their parents. I showed the relevant stratification mechanism in place that enforce this process. But teacher awareness might make the difference. To be aware of the streaming mechanism and thus the stratification in place and to have significant knowledge about the weak points of the Berlin education system regarding the negative influence of SES is what pupils deserve. Every Berlin teacher needs to know where to act and which critical points there are in order to provide equality in opportunity in education, as it each pupil's right. However, quite a large number of them already do so. Structures and support need to be in place to help them achieve equality in opportunity and these need to be provided by education system and those in charge of it.

Primary school teachers need to be aware of their responsibility and have the ability to act accordingly. They can not influence the average mark required to continue school at an advanced high school. However, they can learn about how SES influences performance and accomplishments in early age and try to counteract the disadvantages it provides and in return provide each pupils

with equal chances to achieve the required grade average. Secondary school teachers need to be aware that even if the distinction between advanced and basic high school is based on Primary school performance, there are no stupid pupils. Only pupils with less valued abilities or pupils that had to start from a disadvantaged position. Berlin teachers need to be aware of the education system. As long as there is inequality in educational opportunity, they need to counteract the streaming and stratification in place to provide each pupil with equal chances.

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